

These experiments showed a high extent of protein import as measured by inaccessibility to thermolysin digestion. We conclude that the cDNA from *N. pseudonarcissus* codes for a functional phytoene synthase and thus is suitable for rice transformation.

The cDNA was subcloned under the control of the CaMV35S promoter and glutelin promoter (Burkhardt et al 1996, Potrykus et al 1996). We examined the resulting transformants for phytoene synthase expression. First, reverse-transcriptase polymerase chain reaction was established to detect mRNA of the introduced transgenes in rice endosperm. The results revealed the presence of specific

mRNA, which was absent in endosperm of control plants. Second, using homologous anti-phytoene synthase antibodies, phytoene synthase was detected in transformed endosperm, whereas no signal was obtained in the control plants. Third, using RP-HPLC, the phytoene content was determined in mature rice seeds deprived of the embryo. Phytoene content was usually below detection limit in the controls: in some cases, however, insignificantly low amounts probably derived from seed coat were present.

In contrast, high amounts of phytoene found in seeds of some transformants allowed clear UV/VIS spectra-proving identity to be obtained. Constructs under glutelin promoter control were successful in

phytoene formation. The best line obtained so far showed a phytoene content of 1 µmol per gram (after quantification by calibrated integration on HPLC and use of a molar extinction coefficient of 68,125 mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹). This corresponds to 545 µg phytoene per gram, which is safely within the nutritionally useful range (Burkhardt et al 1996).

Cited references

- Burkhardt PK, Beyer P, Terada R, Kloti A, Wünn J, Lintig JV, Armstrong GA, Potrykus I. 1996. Genetic engineering of provitamin A biosynthesis in rice endosperm. In: Khush GS, ed. Rice genetics III. Manila (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute, p 818-821. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Screening of Basmati rice genotypes against blast

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Blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* Sacc.= *Magnaporthe grisea* (Hebert) Barr., is a devastating disease of scented, tall varieties in Haryana. We screened 175 rice genotypes in station and coordinated trials at the Rice Research Station in Kaul.

For leaf blast screening in the Uniform Blast Screening Nursery, we alternated each test genotype with susceptible variety Taraori Basmati on all sides during the 1993 kharif (dry season). For neck blast screening, 1-mo-old seedlings of test entries were transplanted in two 5-m-long rows at 20- × 15-cm spacing. One line of Taraori Basmati was planted between each test entry to ensure maximum disease development. We recorded leaf blast incidence during the last week of September when the disease was at its peak. Tillers of 25 randomly selected hills of each test entry were examined for neck blast 1 wk before harvest. We scored the disease severity using the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1988). Genotypes showing

Basmati rice genotypes showing resistance to blast. Haryana, India, 1993 and 1994 kharifs.

Leaf blast	Neck blast	Both leaf and neck blast
HKR86-416	HKR90-403	HKR90-403
HKR90-403	HKR90-404	HKR91-405
HKR90-407	HKR91-405	
HKR90-410	HKR91-431	
HKR91-401	RP3121-14-10-2	
HKR91-402	RP3138-60-91-0-6	
HKR91-404	RP3238-38-15-7-1	
HKR91-405	RPST328	
HKR91-408	NDR637-90	
HKR91-413	UPR-BS-92-5	
HKR91-424		
HKR91-427		
HKR91-456		
HKR91-459		
HKR91-460		
HKR91-467		
HKR92-405		
HKR92-409		
HKR239		

resistance to leaf or neck blast were retested during 1994 kharif to confirm their reaction to the disease.

We found 19 genotypes resistant to leaf blast and 10 genotypes to neck blast during both years (see table). Only genotypes HKR90-403 and HKR91-405 showed resistance to both leaf and neck blast. Besides blast, three genotypes (HKR86-416, HKR90-404, and HKR92-405) also exhibited resistance to stem rot. ■

Resistance spectrum, race specificity, and expression of the *Xa21* gene family

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The rice gene *Xa21* confers resistance to the bacterial pathogen *Xanthomonas oryzae* (*Xoo*) (Ikeda et al 1990, Ronald et al 1992). The *Xa21* locus consists of a small multigene family, and transgenic lines (T₀) expressing a single member of the *Xa21* gene family confer resistance to *Xoo* race 6 (Song et al 1996). Unlike all other cloned plant disease resistance genes, the deduced amino acid sequence of *Xa21* encodes a glycosylated leucine-rich repeat (LRR) extracellular domain, a single-pass transmembrane domain, and a serine threonine kinase intracellular domain. The sequence of the predicted protein of *Xa21* strongly suggests its role in cell-surface recognition of a pathogen ligand and subsequent activation of an intracellular defense response.

To determine the resistance spectrum of cloned resistance gene *Xa21*, we tested 300 T₁ progeny from the transgenic line 106-17 containing *Xa21* for *Xoo* resistance.